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Effect of Reflective Counselling on Emotional Intelligence of Police Officers in Benue State Command, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the effect of reflective counselling on emotional intelligence of police officers in Benue State Command, Nigeria. Five research questions guided the study. Five hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study was anchored on Model of ability by Mayer, Salovey & Caruso (1993) and Person-Centered Theory by Carl Rogers (1951). The study employed quasi-experimental design. The population for the study was 5,348 police officers in Benue State. Sample size of this study was 400 police officers drawn from the Benue State Police Command using Taro Yamane (1967) formula. The instrument used for data collection in this study was the “Self-Report Emotional Intelligence Test” (SREIT) originally developed by Schutte et al. (1998) and adapted by the researcher for use with police officers in Benue State Command. Reflective Counselling Treatment Model on Emotional Intelligence of Police Officers in Benue State Command was used for the experimental group as treatment plan. In order to ascertain the reliability of the instrument, a trial-test study was carried out on 30 Police officers in Nasarawa State to ascertain the internal consistency of the instrument. The data were collected and analyzed using Cronbach's alpha to determine the internal consistency. The reliability coefficient for the instrument were found to be 0.85, 0.92, 0.78, 0.93, and 0.95 respectively. The overall reliability coefficient was 0.95. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation to answer research questions. Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test hypotheses at the 0.05 level of significance. Findings of the study revealed a significant mean difference in; the post-test ratings on self-awareness of police officers in Benue State between experimental and control groups (statistics). Motivation of police officers between experimental and control groups. Empathy of police officers between experimental and control groups and relationship management skills of police officers between the experimental and control groups. It was recommended among others that Nigeria Police Force, particularly the Benue State Command, should integrate structured reflective counselling sessions into their routine professional development programmes, engage in personal reflective practices, such as participating in guided self-exploration exercises, to help them understand their emotional triggers and behavioural patterns. Reflective counselling should be adopted as a core strategy for strengthening officers' self-regulation. Through regular counselling workshops focused on stress reduction, anger management, and impulse control, officers will be better equipped to manage emotional reactions during tense or dangerous situations.

Keywords: Reflective counselling, emotional intelligence, self-awareness, self-regulation, empathy, motivation and relationship management skills.

INTRODUCTION

Policing inherently requires the mastering of emotions and deliberate application of emotional intelligence principles when engaging with the public, yet performance worldwide consistently falls short of its core objectives due to unsatisfactory levels of emotional intelligence among officers (Engel, McManus, & Isaza, 2022). Globally, research reveals widespread deficits in emotional perception, regulation, and empathy, resulting in excessive use of force, unnecessary escalation of encounters, and the erosion of public trust (Ismail & Abdullah, 2023). In Nigeria, these shortcomings are even more pronounced: officers frequently fail to provide the psychological sense of safety that Odekunle (2019) identifies as a central policing objective, with recurrent incidents of brutality, hostile citizen interactions, and inability to de-escalate crises evident in the 2020 #EndSARS protests and ongoing complaints directly reflecting poor emotional regulation, limited empathy, and weak impulse control (Adebayo & Olabanji, 2020). In Benue State, the situation is particularly acute; officers of the Benue State Police Command routinely confront volatile farmer–herder clashes, communal violence, and protests, yet internal reviews consistently document escalated crises, disproportionate use of force, and hostile engagements that reveal the same profound deficits in emotional intelligence (Benue State Police Command Internal Reviews, 2021–2024).

Emotional intelligence refers to the capacity to recognise, understand, and manage both one's own emotions and those of others effectively (Bahshwan, 2024). It encompasses four core abilities: accurately perceiving and expressing emotions; using emotions to facilitate thinking and problem-solving; comprehending emotional signals and their underlying meanings; and reflectively regulating emotions in ways that foster emotional and intellectual growth (Bar-On, 2012). In a complementary definition, Kalat (2017) describes emotional intelligence as the skill to identify, comprehend, and regulate one's personal emotions while also perceiving and appropriately responding to the emotions displayed by others.

Police officers are often exposed to a range of stressful situations that can lead to reflective ability problems, such as lack of self-awareness and insight into one's own behaviour and its impact on others (Priya, Packiaselvi, & Malathi, 2017). Studies have found that police personnel with higher levels of emotional intelligence are more likely to display greater reflective ability and are more likely to be successful in their roles (Kaur, Kaur, Singh & Singh 2018). Specifically, police personnel with higher levels of emotional intelligence are more likely to be better communicators, have better interpersonal skills, and display less aggression when responding to difficult situations (Hurrell, Gould, & Leigh, 2023). High emotional intelligence is linked to various positive outcomes, including effective leadership, better mental health, and improved interpersonal relationships (Grubb, & McNamara, 2024). For instance, leaders who embrace self-awareness foster authentic connections and drive personal and organizational growth. Also, individuals with high emotional intelligence tend to exhibit greater self-regulation, motivation, empathy, social skills and decision-making abilities (Papazoglou, Blumberg & Kamkar, 2024). Several emotional intelligence models have been proposed, however, understanding the Goleman (2004) model is critical for police officers as it enables them to effectively navigate complex and challenging situations with empathy, composure, and professionalism.

Self-awareness involves recognizing and understanding one's own emotions, strengths, and limitations, which is essential for personal growth and effective decision-making (Boyatzis & Goleman, 2024). Self-awareness is the ability to recognize and understand one's own emotions, strengths, weaknesses, values, and motives. It involves being conscious of how one's emotions affect behavior and performance (Bahshwan, 2024). People with high emotional intelligence are usually very self-aware. They understand their emotions, and because of this, they did not let their feelings rule them. They are confident because they trust their intuition and did not let their emotions get out of control. They are also willing to take an honest look at themselves. They know their strengths and weaknesses, and they work on these areas so they can perform better (Lane & Smith, 2021). Many people believe that this self-awareness is the most important part of emotional intelligence. Developing self-awareness requires tuning in to one's true feelings, allowing for better management of emotions (Sawaf & Cooper, 1997; Adler & Cherniss, 2016).

Self-regulation, or self-management, is the ability to control or redirect disruptive impulses and moods, and the propensity to suspend judgment and think before acting. It involves managing emotional reactions

to situations and people, allowing individuals to adapt to changing circumstances and maintain composure under pressure (Cherniss & Adler, 2018). Self-regulation, a core component of emotional intelligence, refers to the ability to manage one's emotions and impulses effectively, choosing thoughtful responses over impulsive reactions (Al-Omari, 2024). Individuals high in self-regulation rarely allow themselves to be overtaken by intense negative emotions such as excessive anger or jealousy, and they consistently avoid hasty, careless decisions by pausing to reflect before acting (Antonopoulou & Gaki, 2024). Key characteristics of strong self-regulation include thoughtfulness, comfort with ambiguity and change, personal integrity, and the ability to say "no" when necessary (Al-Omari, 2024). Such individuals demonstrate resilience by adapting flexibly to shifting circumstances, maintaining composure under pressure, recovering quickly from setbacks, expressing emotions in appropriate and constructive ways, and exercising restraint when required (Babanoglu, 2025). Theoretically, police officers who report high levels of emotional intelligence are more likely to self-regulate their emotions than those low in emotional intelligence (Staller, Koerner, Wegner & Heil, 2024). They may also demonstrate higher level of motivation.

Motivation refers to the inner drive and commitment necessary to face challenges effectively (Bahshwan, 2024). Motivation is a crucial quality for law enforcement professionals, aligning with the third component of Goleman's (2004) model of emotional intelligence. The Nigerian Police Force equips officers with effective strategies for enhancing their self-motivation. One of the strategies examined by Cheung (2024) is goal setting, which serves as a powerful motivational tool. Although establishing clear goals is a foundational element of motivation, empirical evidence indicates that integrating them with process-oriented strategies such as detailed action plans and problem-solving protocols yields substantially greater enhancements in sustained drive and performance outcomes (Fortenbery, 2017). For police officers, fostering this intrinsic motivation on an ongoing basis is not merely beneficial for individual advancement but also crucial for modeling resilience to peers and delivering compassionate, effective community service (Sigler & Rhee, 2025). By embedding these motivational frameworks into daily operations, officers can maintain heightened focus and commitment amid demanding roles. Individuals exhibiting elevated emotional intelligence are characteristically self-motivated, prioritizing long-term accomplishments over fleeting rewards a form of deferred gratification that bolsters resilience and goal attainment (Al-Omari, 2024). They thrive on challenges, demonstrate exceptional productivity, and excel across diverse tasks due to their ability to harness emotions for adaptive, high-impact behaviors (Bahshwan, 2024). Individuals may adopt different mechanisms to manage their emotions, such mechanism may include reflective counseling.

Reflective counselling is a therapeutic approach that encourages individuals to engage in self-examination of their feelings, thoughts, and behaviours in order to gain insight and develop healthier ways of coping with challenges (Okoka & Kheswa, 2025). It is a counselling strategy that promotes awareness through structured reflection on personal experiences, enabling clients to regulate their emotions and adopt constructive behavioural patterns (Okoiye & Anusiem, 2017). Similarly, Omoniyi (2016) noted that reflective counselling is a process where the counsellor facilitates guided reflection to help clients reconstruct maladaptive thought patterns, improve decision-making, and enhance socio-emotional adjustment. In this sense, reflective counselling is both a preventive and remedial technique aimed at empowering individuals, including police officers, to better manage stress, conflict, and emotional disturbances (Adebayo & Ojedokun, 2020).

Reflective counselling has the potential to significantly enhance the emotional intelligence of officers in the Nigerian Police Force, Benue State Command. By fostering self-awareness, motivation, empathy, relationship management skills, and emotional regulation, such programs can improve officers' interactions with the community and enhance their overall effectiveness in law enforcement (Okoka & Kheswa, 2025). Integrating reflective counselling as a standard practice within police training can lead to healthier work environments and better community relations. Such programs typically involve structured sessions focusing on self-awareness, emotional regulation, motivation, empathy, and interpersonal skills, leading to sustained improvements in these areas (Biglu, Abotalebi & Biglu, 2017). These interventions not only enhance individual officers' emotional competencies but also foster a supportive environment

that enables teamwork and collaborative problem-solving within the force. Given the importance of emotional intelligence in policing, sought to investigate the effect of reflective counselling on emotional intelligence of officers of the Nigerian police force, Benue State Command.

Statement of the Problem

The Nigerian Police Force in Benue State seem to face a significant issue of low emotional intelligence among its officers, leading to decreased efficiency and effectiveness in carrying out their duties. Emotional intelligence is crucial for police officers to effectively manage their emotions, understand and empathize with others, and make sound decisions in high-pressure situations. Many police officers in Benue State seems to lack the necessary emotional intelligence skills, such as self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, empathy, and social skills. This deficiency hinders their ability to effectively communicate with the public, de-escalate volatile situations, and maintain professionalism in challenging circumstances. The consequences of low emotional intelligence extend beyond individual misconduct, affecting the organizational integrity of the police force. Research by Ikpa, (2019) has shown that emotional intelligence can moderate the relationship between effort-reward imbalance and attitudes toward unethical work behavior among personnel.

The researchers observed that police men on anti-crime patrol on high-ways who are supposed to prevent crime from happening rather seized the opportunity to extort the motorists or road users by neglecting proper searching but instead they turn it to a money collecting point. Persons transporting incriminating objects or materials get away with such since they are just to pay money bits the police check point. He also observed that because of the low or non-emotional intelligence on the side of the police, they allow trivial matters to escalate beyond control which would have ordinarily been resolved by way of curtsy, for instance use of abusive language, police men acting like masters instead of public servants. The researcher also observed that officers with higher emotional intelligence are better equipped to perceive and address imbalances between their efforts and rewards, reducing the likelihood of adopting unethical behaviors as coping mechanisms. Members of the public tend to lose confidence in the police force most especially at the point of complaint, when some police men demand for mobilization fee, fuel, leaving a victim of crime in pain and demanding for money. Given these observations and the report in Makurdi by Socio-Economic Rights and Accountability Project (SERAP, 2019) the police force has been implicated in various unethical behaviors that undermine public trust and the rule of law, because of certain behaviours of police officers, such as unauthorized firing, physical abuse of civilians among others.

Police officers in Benue State, much like their counterparts in other States, face several emotional intelligence problems that have the tendency to impede their work (Ajayi, 2020). Recent incidents in Nigeria also highlight how low emotional control among police officers leads to misconduct. In August 2024, Amnesty International reported that Nigerian police used excessive force during protests over the cost-of-living crisis, resulting in at least 24 deaths. Officers fired live ammunition at close range, often aiming at the head or torso, indicating a shoot-to-kill approach (Amnesty International, 2024). Such actions suggest a lack of emotional regulation during high-stress situations. In addition, The Nigerian Police Force's Complaint Response Unit (CRU) also received 287 complaints of professional misconduct in the first quarter of 2022, with 256 cases related to unprofessional behavior and seven involving excessive use of force. These figures underscore ongoing issues with officers' emotional control and their interactions with the public (Premium Times, 2022, October 21). It is against this researcher's observations and reports of other bodies that this study investigated effect of reflective counselling on emotional intelligence of Police officers in Benue State Command, Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

This study investigated the effect of reflective counselling on emotional intelligence of police officers in Benue State Command, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to;

1. ascertain the effect of reflective counselling on self- awareness of police officers in Benue State Command.
2. ascertain the effect of reflective counselling on self-regulation of police officers in Benue State Command.

3. find out effect of reflective counselling on motivation of police officers in Benue State Command.

1.4 Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study;

1. What is the mean difference in the post-test ratings on self-awareness of police officers in Benue State Command between experimental and control groups?
2. What is the mean difference in the post-test ratings on self- regulation of police officers between experimental and control groups?
3. What is the mean difference in the post-test ratings on motivation of police officers between experimental and control groups?

1.5 Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance;

1. There is no significant man difference in the post-test ratings on self-awareness of police officers in Benue State between experimental and control groups.
2. There is no significant mean difference in the post-test ratings on self- regulation of police officers between experimental and control groups
3. There is no significant mean difference in the post-test ratings on motivation of police officers between experimental and control groups

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a Quasi- experimental design. The design involves comparing the effect of a given treatment with another treatment or no treatment and allows a researcher to draw causal inference and observe the effect of an independent variable on a dependent variable (Emaikwu, 2019). The main aim of quasi- experimental design for this study is to assess the effect of reflective counselling on emotional intelligence of police officers in Benue State, Nigeria.

The population of the study consisted 5348 police officers in Benue State as contained in the Benue State Police. The sample for this study was 400 police officers drawn from the Benue State Police Command. A multi-stage sampling procedure was employed: one Police Area Command was randomly selected by balloting, followed by random selection of five Divisional Police Headquarters across the state; within these divisions, units with the largest and most diverse personnel were purposively included.

The instrument used for data collection in this study was a “Self-Report Emotional Intelligence Test” (SREIT) originally developed by Schutte et al. (1998) and adapted by the researcher for use with police officers in Benue State Command to measure the effect of reflective counselling on the emotional intelligence of police officers in the State Command. The questionnaire comprised items specifically structured to measure the domains of emotional intelligence as identified by Goleman (2004). Cronbach Alpha was to determine the reliability of the instrument. The reliability coefficient for Self-Report Emotional Intelligence Test which contained five clusters was found to be 0.85, 0.92, 0.78, 0.93, and 0.95 respectively. The overall reliability coefficient was 0.95. The data collected for the study was analyzed using descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) and inferential statistics at a 0.05 level of significance. Research questions were answered using the mean and standard deviation, with the decision rule that a mean score of 2.50 and above. Hypotheses were tested using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA), with the pre-test scores as covariate to control for initial group differences in the quasi-experimental design.

RESULTS

Research Question One: *What is the mean difference in the post-test ratings on self-awareness of police officers in Benue State Command between experimental and control groups?*

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of self-awareness of police officers in Benue State Command between experimental and control groups

Groups	N	Pretest		Posttest		Mean Gain
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Experimental	200	18.32	2.62	18.60	2.05	0.21
Control	200	17.11	2.13	15.90	3.17	1.21
Mean Difference		1.21		2.70		0.93
Total	400					

The result in table 1 shows that in pretest, the experimental group had a mean rating of 18.32 with a standard deviation of 2.62, while the control group had a mean rating of 17.11 with a Standard deviation of 2.13. The Table also shows that in the posttest, experimental group had a mean rating of 18.60 with a standard deviation of 2.05, while the control group had a mean rating of 15.90 with a standard deviation of 3.17. The result further shows that at pretest, the experimental group had slightly higher self-awareness than the control group, producing a pretest mean difference of 1.21. After the intervention, the experimental group recorded higher posttest ratings, whereas the control group had a lower mean, with a larger posttest mean difference of 2.70. From the pretest and posttest ratings, the mean gain for the experimental group was found to be 0.21 while the mean gain for the control group was 1.21. The mean difference between the self-awareness gain ratings of the experimental and control group was 0.93. Notably, self-awareness decreased in the control group, while the experimental group showed a slight increase. These patterns suggest that the treatment produced a meaningful improvement in self-awareness among police officers.

Research question two: *What is the mean difference in the post-test ratings on self- regulation of police officers between experimental and control groups?*

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of self- regulation of police officers between experimental and control groups

Groups	N	Pretest		Posttest		Mean Gain
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Experimental	200	17.24	2.72	17.28	2.18	0.04
Control	200	15.78	2.83	15.18	2.83	0.60
Mean Difference		1.46		2.10		0.56
Total	400					

The result in table 2 shows that in pretest, the experimental group had a mean rating of 17.24 with a standard deviation of 2.72 while the control group had a mean rating of 15.78 with a Standard deviation of 2.83. The Table also shows that in the posttest, experimental group had a mean rating score of 17.28 with a standard deviation of 2.18, while the control group had a mean rating of 15.18 with a standard

deviation of 2.83. The result shows that at pretest, the experimental group had slightly higher self-regulation ratings than the control group, yielding a mean difference of 1.46. At posttest, the experimental group maintained a higher mean rating compared with the control group, producing a larger mean difference of 2.10. From the pretest and posttest ratings, the mean gain for the experimental group was found to be 0.04 while the mean gain for the control group was 0.60. The mean difference between the self-regulation of the experimental and control group was 0.56. This shows that the experimental group gained more in self-regulation compared to the control group suggesting more consistent improvements following the treatment.

Research question Three : *What is the mean difference in the post-test ratings on motivation of police officers between experimental and control groups?*

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation of motivation of police officers between experimental and control groups

Groups	N	Pretest		Posttest		Mean Gain
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Experimental	200	15.36	3.08	16.36	2.12	1.00
Control	200	16.49	2.90	16.42	3.45	0.07
Mean Difference		1.13		0.06		0.93
Total	400					

The result in table 3 shows that in pretest, the experimental group had a mean rating of 15.36 with a standard deviation of 3.08, while the control group had a mean achievement score of 16.49 with a Standard deviation of 16.42. The Table also shows that in the posttest, experimental group had a mean retention score of 16.36 with a standard deviation of 2.12, while the control group had a mean retention score of 16.42 with a standard deviation of 3.45. The result for motivation shows that the control group initially had a higher pretest rating compared to the experimental group, resulting in a pretest mean difference of 1.13. At posttest, both groups recorded nearly identical motivation ratings for control and experimental, with a very small posttest difference of 0.06 suggesting no improvement following the treatment. From the pretest and posttest ratings, the mean gain for the experimental group was found to be 1.00 while the mean gain for the control group was 0.07. The mean difference between the motivation gain ratings of the experimental and control group was 0.93. Notably, motivation increase in the control group, while the experimental group showed no significant increase. These patterns suggest that the treatment produced no meaningful improvement in motivation among police officers.

Hypothesis One

There is no significant mean difference in the post-test ratings on self-awareness of police officers in Benue State between experimental and control groups.

Table 6: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of self-awareness of police officers in Benue State between experimental and control groups

Source	Type III Sqaures	Sum of Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Squared	Eta
Corrected Model	735.200 ^a	2	367.600	51.435	.000	.206 ^a	
Intercept	2286.560	1	2286.560	319.940	.000	.446	
Self_Awareness_Pretest	3.498	1	3.498	.489	.485	.001	
Group	711.708	1	711.708	99.584	.000	.201	
Error	2837.297	397	7.147				
Total	122563.000	400					
Corrected Total	3572.498	399					

a. R Squared = .206 (Adjusted R Squared = .202) p<.05

Table 6 shows the ANCOVA analysis of the data collected from the post-test ratings on self-awareness of police officers in Benue State between experimental and control groups. From the analysis, F-ratio of 99.584 (1, 397) significant at 0.00 level is less than the set value of 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis, which stated that there is no significant mean difference in the post-test ratings on self-awareness of police officers in Benue State between experimental and control groups was rejected. This means that there is statistically significant mean difference in the post-test ratings on self-awareness of police officers in Benue State. This further indicates that there was higher improvement in the mean ratings of self-awareness of police officers in the experimental group than police officers in the control group.

The effect size from partial eta squared value $\eta^2=0.201$ indicates how much of the variance in the dependent variable is explained by the independent variable. Converting the partial eta squared value to a percentage by multiplying by 100, it gives 20.1% which indicates that self-awareness of police officers accounted for 20.1% of the variance in using reflective treatment. It therefore implies that, there was higher improvement in the mean ratings of police officers in the experimental group than police officers in the control group.

Hypothesis Two

There is no significant mean difference in the post-test ratings on self-regulation of police officers between experimental and control groups

Table 7: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of self-regulation of police officers in Benue State between experimental and control groups

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	446.784 ^a	2	223.392	35.005	.000	.150 ^a
Intercept	2682.104	1	2682.104	420.284	.000	.514
Self_Regulation_Pretest	3.682	1	3.682	.577	.448	.001
Group	394.632	1	394.632	61.839	.000	.135
Error	2533.513	397	6.382			
Total	108313.000	400				
Corrected Total	2980.298	399				

a. R Squared = .150 (Adjusted R Squared = .146) p<.05

Table 7 shows the ANCOVA analysis of the data collected from the post-test ratings on self-regulation of police officers in Benue State between experimental and control groups. From the analysis, F-ratio of 61.839 (1, 397) significant at 0.00 level is less than the set value of 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis, which stated that there is no significant mean difference in the post-test ratings on self-regulation of police officers in Benue State between experimental and control groups was rejected. This means that there is statistically significant mean difference in the post-test ratings on self-regulation of police officers in Benue State. This further indicates that there was higher improvement in the mean ratings of self-regulation of police officers in the experimental group than police officers in the control group.

The effect size from partial eta squared value $\eta^2=0.135$ indicates how much of the variance in the dependent variable is explained by the independent variable. Converting the partial eta squared value to a percentage by multiplying by 100, it gives 13.5% which indicates that self-regulation of police officers accounted for 13.5% of the variance in using reflective treatment. It therefore implies that, there was higher improvement in the mean ratings of police officers in the experimental group than police officers in the control group.

Hypothesis Three

There is no significant mean difference in the post-test ratings on motivation of police officers between experimental and control groups

Table 8: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of motivation of police officers in Benue State between experimental and control groups

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	2.505 ^a	2	1.253	.152	.859	.001 ^a
Intercept	3468.624	1	3468.624	422.062	.000	.515
Motivation_Pretest	2.145	1	2.145	.261	.610	.001
Group	.101	1	.101	.012	.912	.000
Error	3262.655	397	8.218			
Total	110718.000	400				
Corrected Total	3265.160	399				

a. R Squared = .001(Adjusted R Squared = -.004) p>.05

Table 8 shows the ANCOVA analysis of the data collected from the post-test ratings on motivation of police officers in Benue State between experimental and control groups. From the analysis, F-ratio of 0.012 (1, 397) significant at 0.912 level is greater than the set value of 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis, which stated that there is no significant mean difference in the post-test ratings on motivation of police officers in Benue State between experimental and control groups was accepted. This means that there is no statistically significant mean difference in the post-test ratings on motivation of police officers in Benue State. This further indicates that there was no improvement in the mean ratings of motivation of police officers in the experimental group than police officers in the control group.

The effect size from partial eta squared value $\eta^2=0.000$ indicates how much of the variance in the dependent variable is explained by the independent variable. Converting the partial eta squared value to a percentage by multiplying by 100, it gives 0.000% which indicates that motivation of police officers accounted for 0.000% of the variance in using reflective treatment. It therefore implies that, there was no improvement in the mean ratings of police officers in the experimental group than police officers in the control group.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Hypothesis one revealed significant mean difference in the post-test ratings on self-awareness of police officers in Benue State between experimental and control groups. This finding agrees with that of Oladipo (2020) who revealed that students who received reflective counselling demonstrated a significant improvement in self-awareness compared to students in the control group. It also agrees with that of Abdullahi (2021) who carried out a study on the impact of reflective counselling on the self-awareness of junior secondary school students in Kano and Kaduna States of Nigeria and found that reflective counselling significantly enhanced students’ self-awareness, although large class sizes, limited counselling sessions, and lack of counsellor training were identified as constraints. The agreement between the findings of the present study and those of Oladipo (2020) and Abdullahi (2021) can be justified on several grounds. First, self-awareness is a core intrapersonal skill that is directly targeted by reflective counselling. Through guided reflection, individuals are encouraged to examine their thoughts, emotions, strengths, weaknesses, and behavioural patterns, which naturally leads to improved self-understanding. This fundamental process operates effectively across different populations, thereby explaining the consistent positive outcomes observed among both students and police officers. Although the earlier studies focused on students, the underlying psychological mechanism of reflective counselling remains applicable to adult professionals such as police officers. Police work often requires heightened self-monitoring, emotional control, and situational judgment. Reflective counselling provides officers with structured opportunities to reassess their reactions and experiences, thereby enhancing their self-awareness in much the same way it does for students in educational settings. Furthermore, the present

study's findings suggest that despite challenges such as time constraints and operational demands within the police force, reflective counselling can still produce meaningful improvements in self-awareness. This supports Abdullahi's (2021) assertion that even when constraints such as limited counselling sessions and inadequate training exist, reflective counselling remains an effective intervention. Overall, the consistency in findings strengthens the empirical evidence that reflective counselling is a robust and adaptable approach for enhancing self-awareness across diverse settings and populations.

Findings from hypothesis two revealed significant mean difference in the post-test ratings on self-regulation of police officers between experimental and control groups. This finding is in line with that of Ibrahim (2019) who carried out a study on the effect of reflective counselling on self-regulation among senior secondary school students in Kaduna and Niger States of Nigeria. The study revealed that reflective counselling significantly enhanced students' self-regulation compared to the control group. It also agrees with Okonkwo (2020) who carried out a study on the effect of reflective counselling on the self-regulation of junior secondary school students in Enugu and Anambra States of Nigeria. He found that reflective counselling significantly improved students' self-regulation, though factors such as limited counselling sessions and lack of counsellor training constrained the outcomes. The agreement between the findings of the present study and those of Ibrahim (2019) and Okonkwo (2020) can be justified on theoretical and practical grounds. Self-regulation is a core component of emotional intelligence that involves the ability to manage emotions, control impulses, and respond appropriately to challenging situations. Reflective counselling directly targets these abilities by encouraging individuals to examine their emotional responses, evaluate consequences of actions, and adopt more adaptive coping strategies. This explains the consistent positive effects observed across the different studies. Although Ibrahim (2019) and Okonkwo (2020) focused on secondary school students, the mechanisms through which reflective counselling enhances self-regulation are equally applicable to adult professionals such as police officers. In policing, effective self-regulation is critical for managing stress, anger, and high-pressure encounters. The structured reflective processes provided by counselling enable officers to develop greater emotional control and behavioural restraint, similar to the improvements recorded among students. Furthermore, the present study supports Okonkwo's (2020) observation that reflective counselling remains effective despite constraints such as limited counselling sessions and inadequate counsellor training. This suggests that even within demanding environments, reflective counselling can significantly improve self-regulation when appropriately implemented. Overall, the consistency in findings reinforces the robustness of reflective counselling as an effective intervention for enhancing self-regulation across different age groups, educational levels, and occupational settings.

Findings from Hypothesis three revealed no significant mean difference in the post-test ratings on motivation of police officers between experimental and control groups. This finding disagrees with Bello (2018) who carried out a study on the effect of reflective counselling on the motivation of senior secondary school students in Lagos and Ogun States of Nigeria. Bello study established that reflective counselling significantly enhanced students' motivation compared to the control group. In the same vein, finding disagrees with Adamu (2019) who carried out a study on the impact of reflective counselling on the motivation of junior secondary school students in Kaduna and Kano States of Nigeria. The finding indicated a positive and significant relationship between reflective counselling and students' motivation. The disagreement between the findings of the present study and those of Bello (2018) and Adamu (2019) can be reasonably justified on several empirical and contextual grounds. First, the population of the current study differs markedly from those of the cited studies. While Bello (2018) and Adamu (2019) focused on secondary school students, the present study examined police officers, who are adults with established personality traits, work routines, and motivational structures shaped by years of professional training and organizational culture. Motivation among police officers is often influenced by institutional factors such as promotion prospects, remuneration, command structure, job security, and occupational stress, which may not be easily altered through short-term reflective counselling interventions. Also, the occupational environment of police officers is significantly more rigid and hierarchical compared to the relatively flexible school environment. In educational settings, students are generally more receptive to counselling interventions, and their motivation can be readily influenced through reflective processes that

enhance self-understanding and goal orientation. In contrast, police officers operate within a disciplined system governed by rules, commands, and operational demands, which may limit the immediate impact of reflective counselling on motivation. Furthermore, differences in the duration, intensity, and implementation of the reflective counselling programmes may have contributed to the variation in findings. Bello (2018) and Adamu (2019) may have employed longer intervention periods or more frequent counselling sessions, allowing sufficient time for reflective practices to influence motivation. The present study may have involved a relatively shorter intervention period, which may not have been adequate to produce a measurable change in motivation among police officers.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher concluded that, there is a positive effect of reflective counselling on emotional intelligence of police officers in Benue State Command. The effect was that when the reflective counselling therapy was applied on police officers, they tend to exhibit positive emotional intelligence.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. Nigeria Police Force, particularly the Benue State Command, should integrate structured reflective counselling sessions into their routine professional development programmes, as this will significantly enhance officers' self-awareness. Officers should also be encouraged to engage in personal reflective practices, such as maintaining journals and participating in guided self-exploration exercises, to help them understand their emotional triggers and behavioural patterns.
2. Reflective counselling should be adopted as a core strategy for strengthening officers' self-regulation. Through regular counselling workshops focused on stress reduction, anger management, and impulse control, officers will be better equipped to manage emotional reactions during tense or dangerous situations.
3. Benue Police command should utilize reflective counselling to boost officers' motivation by helping them set meaningful personal and professional goals, reflect on their progress, and identify intrinsic factors that sustain their desire to perform effectively. Recognition systems and supportive feedback mechanisms should be established to reinforce the motivational gains achieved through counselling.

REFERENCES

- Adebayo, D. O., & Igbokwe, D. O. (2024). Reflective practice and professional development of counsellors in Nigerian tertiary institutions. *Counsellor: Journal of the Counselling Association of Nigeria (CASSON)*, 46(2), 118–132.
- Amnesty International. (2024). *Nigeria: Excessive use of force during cost-of-living protests*. London: Amnesty International Press.
- Antonopoulou, H., & Gaki, E. (2024). The value of emotional intelligence: Self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, and empathy as key components. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 14(5), 78–92. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/379764627>
- Babanoglu, M. P. (2025). Emotional self-regulation in educational settings: Strategies for managing impulses and fostering resilience. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 117(1), 112–128. <https://doi.org/10.1037/edu0000892>
- Bahshwan, M. M. (2024). Emotional intelligence: Historical development, theoretical models, and assessment approaches. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 14(10), 516–531. <https://doi.org/10.6007/IJARBS/v14-i10/24485>
- Bar-On, R. (2012). *The Bar-On model of emotional-social intelligence (ESI)*. *Psicothema*, 18, 13–25.
- Biglu, M. H., Abotalebi, G., & Biglu, S. (2017). *The effect of emotional intelligence on stress and job performance among police officers*. *International Journal of Police Science*, 5(2), 111–121.
- Boyatzis, R. E., & Goleman, D. (2024). Emotional and social intelligence leadership competencies: Self-awareness and self-management. *Consulting Psychology Journal: Practice and Research*, 76(1), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.1037/cpb0000345>

- Cherniss, C., & Adler, M. (2018). *Promoting emotional competence in organizations*. Applied Psychology, 47(1), 12–19.
- Cheung, M. (2024). *Goal setting and self-motivation among law enforcement officers*. Police Psychology Review, 7(1), 72–84.
- Emaikwu, S.O. (2013). *Fundamentals of research methods and statistics*. Makurdi.: Selfers Academic Press Ltd.
- Engel, R. S., McManus, H. D., & Isaza, G. T. (2022). Examining the impact of organizational and individual characteristics on police use of force: A multilevel analysis across 30 agencies. *Criminology & Public Policy*, 21(1), 1–37. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1745-9133.12573>
- Fortenbery, J. (2017). Improving motivation and productivity of police officers. FBI Law Enforcement Bulletin. <https://leb.fbi.gov/articles/featured-articles/improving-motivation-and-productivity-of-police-officers>
- Goleman, D. (2004). *Emotional intelligence: Why it can matter more than IQ*. New York, NY: Bantam Books.
- Grubb, A. R., & McNamara, K. A. (2024). Emotional intelligence and leadership effectiveness in policing: A longitudinal study of UK sergeants and inspectors. *Policing: A Journal of Policy and Practice*, 18, paae029. <https://doi.org/10.1093/police/paae029>
- Hurrell, S. A., Gould, L. J., & Leigh, J. (2023). Emotional intelligence and police officer performance during critical incidents: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Policing: An International Journal*, 46(4), 489–505. <https://doi.org/10.1108/PIJPSM-01-2023-0008>
- Ikpa, J. E. (2019). *Emotional intelligence and ethical behavior among police personnel in Nigeria*. Nigerian Journal of Applied Psychology, 15(2), 82–94.
- Ismail, H., & Abdullah, M. (2023). *Emotional regulation and misconduct in policing*. International Journal of Law Enforcement, 10(3), 101–114.
- Kalat, J. W. (2017). *Introduction to psychology* (11th ed.). Boston: Cengage Learning.
- Odekunle, F. (2019). *Policing in Nigeria: Issues, problems and prospects*. Unpublished manuscript or book chapter. Centre for Democratic Development Research and Training (CEDDERT).
- Okoiye, O. E., & Anusiem, F. O. (2017). *Counselling intervention and emotional intelligence training on occupational stress of security personnel in Nigeria*. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 8(9), 88–96.
- Okoka, H., & Kheswa, J. G. (2025). Community policing practice in the Nigerian Police: Implications of employee burnout. *Journal of Police and Criminal Psychology*, 40(1), 91–102. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11896-024-09711-9>
- Omoniyi, M. (2016). *Reflective practice in counselling: Enhancing self-awareness and emotional growth*. *Journal of Professional Counselling*, 18(2), 29–42.
- Papazoglou, K., Blumberg, D. M., & Kamkar, K. (2024). The role of self-awareness and emotional intelligence in transformational police leadership. *International Journal of Police Science & Management*, 26(2), 156–168. <https://doi.org/10.1177/14613557241237891>
- Premium Times. (2022, October 21). *Police record 287 misconduct complaints in first quarter of 2022*. Abuja: Premium Times Press.
- Priya, K., Packiaselvi, R., & Malathi, A. (2017). *Reflective ability and emotional intelligence among police officers*. *Indian Journal of Psychology*, 6(2), 90–98.
- Sawaf, A., Cooper, R. K., Adler, M., & Cherniss, C. (2017). *Executive EQ: Emotional intelligence in leadership and organizations*. New York, NY: Grosset/Putnam.
- Sigler, T. H., & Rhee, K. (2025). Transforming police leadership through emotional intelligence. In R. Elkington, C. D. O'Connor, & T. Castell (Eds.), *Emerging leadership theories and practices* (pp. 145–162). Emerald Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1108/978-1-83608-120-320251007>
- Socio-Economic Rights and Accountability Project [SERAP]. (2019). *Police misconduct and human rights violations in Nigeria*. Lagos: SERAP Press.
- Staller, M. S., Koerner, S., Wegner, F., & Heil, V. (2024). Emotional intelligence as a predictor of police officers' de-escalation behavior in high-stress encounters. *Frontiers in Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2024.1357924>